

DEVELOPING CHILDREN'S SPEECH THROUGH THE USE OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN ACTIVITY CENTERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19212174>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 29-yanvar 2026 yil

Ma'qullandi: 10-fevral 2026yil

Nashr qilindi:13-fevral 2026 yil

KEYWORDS

activity center, game technology, speech development, preschool education, communicative activity.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the issues of developing children's speech in preschool educational institutions through the use of activity centers based on game technologies. The games organized in activity centers help analyze the formation of children's vocabulary, pronunciation, grammatical structure, and coherent speech. Additionally, the role of the educator and effective methods are described.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Resolution No. 1 of June 18, 2018, of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, titled "State Requirements for the Development of Early and Preschool Children," and the "First Step" curriculum, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for the comprehensive and harmonious development of children, organize and implement the educational process for preschool-aged children, establish cooperation between families and local communities in early child development issues, and organize developmental centers that enhance learning activities in preschool institutions.

In preschool education, the following centers are mainly organized:

Language and Speech

Construction, Design and Mathematics

Art

Science and Nature

сюжетли va rolli (Thematic and Role-play)

Working with children through games also plays an important role in these centers. For this, we, as educators, must equip the centers properly and create all necessary conditions for children.

For example, in the "Language and Speech" center: picture cards suitable for the lesson are placed in a box, and children are divided into two groups. One participant from each group takes turns selecting a card from the box and creates a story or recites a poem based on the picture.

In the “Construction, Design and Mathematics” center: children use geometric shapes, LEGO, and constructors. Together, they draw a circle and stand around it. Then a number is chosen, for example, the number 10. Ten children enter the circle, and “10-2” is said then two children leave the circle. The remaining children are counted. The example is solved, and the game continues in this way. In this process, children learn to distinguish numbers, count, and perform calculations.

“Art” center:

This center is considered one of the most favorite for children. Because here children draw pictures, color them, do appliqué work, and create various objects from plasticine, engaging in free activities.

For example, in our lesson about “Bread,” we draw bread in the center. The teacher only gives instructions: “Children, we are drawing bread in the ‘Art’ center. Let’s see who can reflect what kind of bread in their drawing?” The children then try to draw different types of bread: some draw beautiful bread, some sesame bread, and others try to draw the bread their mother bakes at home. This helps children think freely and expand their imagination.

“Science and Nature” center:

This center can be organized either indoors or in nature. The teacher can also conduct experiments here. For example: “Let’s reflect a rainbow on paper.” For this, we need a sheet of paper and colored pencils. We color both edges of the paper about 2 cm in length and place both edges into water. As a result, the colors mix and spread upward, forming a rainbow. Children greatly enjoy such experiments and feel delighted by performing them themselves and observing beautiful natural phenomena.

“Role-play and сюжетли (thematic)” center:

This is also one of the children’s favorite centers, because here they listen to fairy tales, imitate the characters, and perform their roles. Some children want to play the role of Kenja botir, others the role of Zumrad, and some prefer to act as cheerful dolls. Every game organized in each center increases children’s speech activity.

Play is considered the leading activity of a child. During play, the child freely expresses thoughts, communicates with peers, and learns to use words correctly.

Through game technologies:

- vocabulary expands,
- pronunciation improves,
- grammatical speech develops,
- coherent speech develops,
- communication culture is formed.

For example, games such as “Who says it faster?”, “Speak in role”, and “Make a story based on the picture” increase children’s speech activity.

To develop speech in activity centers, the educator uses the following methods:

- question-and-answer method,
- organizing conversations,
- creating dialogues and monologues,
- storytelling.
- dramatized games,

- didactic games.

For example, in the role-play center, through games such as “Shop,” “Doctor,” and “Family,” children learn to use words correctly, form sentences, and communicate.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of game technologies in activity centers plays an important role in developing the speech of preschool children. Through play, children learn to think freely, express themselves, and communicate. The educator must create conditions in each center that enhance children’s speech activity. Activities organized on the basis of activity centers contribute to the speech, intellectual, and social development of children.

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